

THE INFLUENCE OF DIFFERENT FACTORS IN THE CULTIVATION OF COTTON VARIETIES ON THE WEIGHT OF COTTON IN ONE SNAP

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Abstract: The article presents data on the influence of seedling thickness, irrigation method and fertilization standards on the weight of cotton per bag of cotton varieties in the conditions of moderately saline grazing light gray soils of the Syrdarya region, based on the biological characteristics of cotton varieties.

Key words: Soil and climate conditions of Syrdarya region, light-colored gray soils that are becoming saline pastures, irrigation methods, fertilizer standards, cotton weight per bag.

INTRODUCTION

In the cotton-growing countries of the world, special attention is being paid to the development of advanced methods of growing technologies of high and quality crops from cotton varieties in the face of global climate change. From this point of view, it is urgent to carry out research in the cultivation of fast-growing and fruitful new varieties of cotton in different soil and climatic conditions, taking into account the special biological characteristics of the crops in the application of one-time irrigation, seasonal irrigation and annual mineral fertilizers.

Special attention is being paid to the development of new technologies that can ensure the production of abundant and high-quality cotton that meets the requirements of world standards due to the rational and efficient use of land, water and natural resources in the cotton industry of our republic. Paragraph 3.3 of the Strategy of Actions for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 states that special attention should be paid to "introduction of modern agro-technologies of new cotton varieties in the field of agricultural production"². Therefore, based on the biological characteristics of the cotton varieties grown in the cotton fields of our republic, it is determined to conduct scientific research on the development of optimal seedling thickness, fertilizer

(NPK) norms and irrigation procedures, and to pay special attention to the implementation of the developed innovative developments.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5742 of June 17, 2019 "On measures for effective use of land and water resources in agriculture", No. PF-5853 of October 23, 2019 "Approval of the strategy for the development of agriculture in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030 on" No. PQ-4243 of 2019, Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 985 of December 12, 2019 "On placement of cotton by varieties in 2020 and forecast volumes of raw cotton cultivation" and other regulatory legal documents related to this activity this dissertation serves to a certain extent.

The purpose of the study: Based on the biological properties of cotton varieties, it is necessary to develop the thickness of seedlings, irrigation method and fertilization standards for obtaining a high and high-quality harvest in the conditions of moderately saline grazing light gray soils of the Syrdarya region.

Research conditions and methods: During field experiments, biological measurements and soil samples were conducted based on the manuals "Metodika Gosudarstvennogo sortoispytaniya selkhozkultur", "Metodika polevykh opytov s xlopchatnikom v usloviyax oroshenie". Agrophysical and agrochemical analyzes of soil samples were determined according to "Metody agrokhimicheskikh analizov pochvy rasteniy Sredney Azii", net photosynthesis productivity was determined according to the method of N.N. Tretyakov, "Methods of conducting field experiments", economic efficiency was determined according to the method of R.A. Baronov. Mathematical-statistical analysis of the data was carried out using the Microsoft Excel program based on the method of B.A. Dosphehov.

The obtained results and their analysis: In the conditions of moderately saline grazing light gray soils, the location depth of seepage water and the amount of harmful salts in the active layer of the soil where the roots spread and the standard ratio of mineral fertilizers are integrally dependent on the weight of cotton in one bag and productivity indicators. In turn, optimal planting thickness, mineral fertilizer rates and irrigation procedures are also very important.

In the experimental field, cotton samples were collected from all pre-harvested, i.e., labeled plants, optimally opened bolls from each variant and returns, and the average weight of one boll of cotton per variant was determined.

Before harvesting, it became known that in 2015-2017, the soil moisture before irrigation in the Sultan cotton variety was in the order of 70-70-65% compared to ChDNS, the annual rate of fertilizers was N180, R126, K90 kg/ha, and the seedling thickness was 80-90 thousand bushels/ha according to the results, the average weight of cotton in one bush is equal to 5.2 grams, and when the thickness of the seedling is increased to 100-110 thousand bush/ha, it is 5.0 grams. When the annual rate of fertilizers is increased from N180, R126, K90 kg/ha to N220, R154, K110 kg/ha, when the seedling thickness is 80-90 thousand bushels/ha, according to returns, the average weight of cotton in one bush is equal to 5.5 grams, and the seedling thickness is 100- It was 5.3 grams when it was increased to 110,000 bushels/ha. The analysis of the data obtained above showed that when the rate of fertilizer increased, the weight of cotton in the boll increased by 0.2 grams.

In the S-6524 cotton variety, soil moisture before irrigation is in the order of 70-70-65% compared to ChDNS, the annual rate of fertilizers is N180, R126, K90 kg/ha, the average weight of cotton in one boll is 5, It was equal to 1 gram, and when the seedling thickness was increased to 100-110 thousand bush/ha, it was 4.9 grams, it was observed that the weight of cotton in one bush decreased by 0.2 grams in exchange for the seedling thickness. When the rate of annual fertilizers is increased from N180, R126, K90 kg/ha to N220, R154, K110 kg/ha, when the seedling thickness is 80-90 thousand bushels/ha, according to returns, the average weight of cotton in one bush is equal to 5.4 grams, and the seedling thickness is 100- It was 5.2 grams when it was increased to 110,000 bushels/ha. The analysis of the data obtained above showed that when the rate of fertilizer increased up to 0.2 grams, the weight of cotton in the boll was higher.

According to the varieties of cotton, Sultan cotton variety compared to S-6524 cotton variety, soil moisture before irrigation is 70-70-65% according to ChDNS, the annual rate of fertilizers is N180, R126, K90 kg/ha, and the seedling thickness is 80-90 thousand bushels/ha. on average, the weight of cotton in one bush is 0.1 grams higher, and it can be seen that it is also 0.1 grams higher when the seedling thickness is increased to 100-110 thousand bush/ha. When the rate of annual fertilizers is increased by N220, R154, K110 kg/ha, the average weight of cotton in one bush is 0.1 grams according to the returns when the seedling thickness is 80-90 thousand bush/ha, and also by 0.1 gram when the seedling thickness is increased to 100-110 thousand bush/ha we can emphasize that it was high.

Soil moisture before irrigation in Sultan cotton variety is 75-75-65% relative to ChDNS, the annual rate of fertilizers is N180, R126, K90 kg/ha, when the seedling thickness is 80-90 thousand bushels/ha, the average weight of cotton in one bush is 5.5 grams. was equal, when the seedling thickness was increased to 100-110,000 bushels/ha, it was 5.3 grams, it was observed that the weight of cotton in one bush decreased by 0.2 grams in exchange for the seedling thickness. When the annual rate of fertilizers is increased from N180, R126, K90 kg/ha to N220, R154, K110 kg/ha, when the seedling thickness is 80-90 thousand bushels/ha, according to returns, the average weight of cotton in one bush is equal to 5.7 grams, and the seedling thickness is 100- It was 5.5 grams when it was increased to 110,000 bushels/ha. The analysis of the data obtained above showed that when the rate of fertilizer increased, the weight of cotton in the boll increased by 0.2 grams.

In the S-6524 cotton variety, soil moisture before irrigation is in the order of 75-75-65% compared to ChDNS, the annual rate of fertilizers is N180, R126, K90 kg/ha, the average weight of cotton in one boll is 5, It was equal to 3 grams, and when the seedling thickness was increased to 100-110 thousand bush/ha, it was 5.1 grams, and it was observed that the weight of cotton in one bush decreased by 0.2 grams in exchange for the seedling thickness. When the annual rate of fertilizers is increased from N180, R126, K90 kg/ha to N220, R154, K110 kg/ha, when the seedling thickness is 80-90 thousand bushels/ha, according to returns, the average weight of cotton in one bush is equal to 5.5 grams, and the seedling thickness is 100- It was 5.3 grams when it was increased to 110,000 bushels/ha. The analysis of the data obtained above showed that when the rate of fertilizer increased up to 0.2 grams, the weight of cotton in the boll was higher. Sultan cotton variety compared to S-6524 cotton variety, pre-irrigation soil moisture is in the order of 75-75-65% according to ChDNS, annual rate of fertilizers is N180, R126, K90 kg/ha, and when the seedling thickness is 80-90 thousand bushels/ha, the average returns are one cup.

Summary: Compared to ChDNS, cotton weight per boll was significantly heavier in 75-75-65% arrangements than in 70-70-65% arrangements. In particular: in the Sultan cotton variety, compared to the 2-3-4-5 options, it was 0.2-0.3 grams higher in the 10-11-12-13 options. The above situation was also reflected in the S-6524 cotton variety, that is, it was higher by 0.1-0.2 grams in the 14-15-16-17 variants than in the 6-7-8-9 variants. Soil moisture before irrigation was 75-75-65% in Sultan and S-6524 cotton varieties, and averaged 5.7-5.5 grams.

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